

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

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INTRODUCTION:

India is one of the biggest underdeveloped countries in the world. India is having near about 7 lakh villages & 110 corers population.

Now India is developing in almost all the fields such as agriculrue, road, trade, communication, international trade, education, development in industrial sector and social welfare etc. The credit of this development goes to entrepreneurship.

But unemployment in rural area in India is serious problem before due to disguised unemployment.

Rural unemployment particularly rural unemployment is basic problem of rural economy in India. Elimination of this problem is one of the important activities of our government. So now-a-days rural women entrepreneurship has given more importance in rural economic development.

MEANING OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP:

“Entrepreneur is the economic agent who utilizes all means of production systematically”.

Number of Economist and expert developed the definitions and expressed the views about entrepreneurship.

RURAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROBLEMS & PROSPECTS:

PROBLEMS:

1) Economic and financial problems

- i) Lack of availability of loan facility.
- ii) Lack of own funds and financial resources.
- iii) Limited working capital
- iv) Constant need of finances
- v) Ignorance of banking procedures and formalities.
- vi) Delay in payment of bills
- vii) Economic incredibility of women
- viii) Lack of collateral security
- ix) Lack of knowledge of accounting
- x) Non availability of any agency to guide and advise on identification of investment opportunities.

2) Lack of knowledge

- i) Lack of knowledge of various schemes run by government.
- ii) Lack of knowledge of different laws and legal aspects.

3) Educational problems

- i) Lack of education and particularly technical education.
- ii) Lack of knowledge of agencies and institutions assisting entrepreneurs.
- iii) Lack of knowledge of loan schemes and procedures of financial institutions.

4) Technological problems

- i) Lack of technical know-how about running the unit.

- ii) Lack of specialised skill to work on specific projects due to incompetence.
- iii) Unable to work in project round the year.
- iv) Lack of facilities for communicating to women entrepreneurs about development and availability of modern technologies.
- v) Difficulty in maintenance and repairs of machinery.

5) Raw material problems

- i) Non availability of required input.
- ii) Lack of continuous supply of raw material for uninterrupted production.
- iii) Time consuming producers for procurement of raw material.
- iv) Variations in raw material prices at different places.
- v) Lack of sufficient stock of raw material in period of short supply and anticipated price change due to poor inventory management.

6) Marketing problems

- i) Lack of marketing experience and poor knowledge of markets.
- ii) Competition from established and larger units.
- iii) Delayed disposal of produce due to inadequate sales promotional avenues and lack of contract with the middlemen.
- iv) Difficulty in getting money, after sale, from buyers.
- v) Lack of sufficient finished goods for smooth sales operations and efficient customer service.
- vi) Excessive dependence on middlemen and exploitation by them.

7) Managerial problems

- i) Lack of clear-cut objectives.
- ii) Lack of planning.
- iii) Poor management.
- iv) Poor project implementation.
- v) Lack of decision-making.

- vi) Incompetent in handling technical, financial, sale and manufacturing activities.
- vii) Lack of managerial skill.

PROSPECTS:

INTRODUCTION:

50% quota declared as reserved for rural women in the field of politics. Therefore their future is delightful in different fields.

1) Opportunity to encourage in entrepreneurship

Recently the rural women entrepreneurship are having the opportunities of the entrepreneurship through the different plans and programmes assigned by the central & state government for the rural areas particularly. This increases the rural women entrepreneurship.

2) Increase in Standard of Living

In India after 1991 privatization, not only entered in the field of Information Technology but also in various product sectors in urban in rural areas, therefore it creates opportunities for rural women entrepreneurship, so it leads to increase the standard of leading.

3) Participation in social & economic growth of rural & urban level

I would like to say entrepreneurship rural areas for women also encourages participation of women in social & other economic activities.

4) It helps to develop economic status

Rural women entrepreneurship also proves economic status of these people is developing.

5) Bachat Gat is the source to develop the rural entrepreneurship

Recently the rural women entrepreneurship is slowly developing due to the important source of Bachat Gat among the number of resources.

CONCLUSION:

In the conclusion I would like to say that rural women entrepreneurship has number of problems such as lack of knowledge, educational problems, economic and financial problems, technological problems, raw material problems etc.

Government of India & state governments are trying to develop women entrepreneurship therefore in future rural women are having an opportunity to develop themselves. If it is undertaken by the government efficiently & effectively then only the slogan of Mahatma Gandhi, 'Rural development is the backbone of overall economic development of India' comes true.

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